

THE UNREST

RMN NEWS MAGAZINE ON ECONOMIC AND POLITICAL UPHEAVALS IN THE WORLD

India Corruption Research Report 2025

An Analysis of Systemic Decay and Democratic Backsliding

AN EDITORIAL INITIATIVE OF RAMAN MEDIA NETWORK (RMN)

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AI Image

India Corruption Research Report

The report has unveiled an assessment of corruption in India, concluding that corruption is now systemic, rooted in the governance frameworks. [Read More](#)

UNITE – Brave NATO Initiative

NATO and Ukraine have launched a significant new joint initiative aimed at accelerating defense innovation: the UNITE – Brave NATO programme. [Read More](#)

Chandigarh Governance Proposal

The Union Home Ministry issued a swift clarification regarding a controversial proposal to alter the legislative structure of the Union Territory of Chandigarh. [Read More](#)

Delhi's Pollution Crisis

Every winter, Delhi enters a familiar and troubling phase: the sky darkens into a grey sheet, visibility drops, and the city begins to breathe heavily. [Read More](#)

Convention to Boost Co-production of Audiovisual Series

The new Council of Europe convention marks a significant step for the European and international audiovisual sector. Its primary goal is to strengthen cultural cooperation, support independent producers, and enhance transparency within this fast-moving industry. [Read More](#)

Delhi High Court e-Filing Failure

Even as the Delhi High Court's e-filing portal remains nonfunctional, grievance authorities have closed complaints without addressing the underlying problem. [Read More](#)

Copytrack's Intimidation Campaign

A growing number of users from around the world have reported being targeted by Germany-based Copytrack, which claims to enforce copyright protections. [Read More](#)

Delhi's Dual Air Crisis

The NCR faced a deterioration in air quality, pushing Delhi to the brink of the 'severe' category. Toxic air is the leading cause of death in the city. [Read More](#)

Him Hit CGHS Corruption Notice

The Clean House service has released the details of a corruption complaint filed by residents of Him Hit CGHS (Sadbhavna Apartments), Dwarka. [Read More](#)

Storybooks Teach Technology to Children

"Raman's Tech Tale Series – Knowledge Stories for Children," is a book series aimed to spread technology awareness among children through short stories. All books in the series are equally useful for children in all parts of the world. [Read More](#)

ITU Strategy to Connect the World

WTDC-25 in Baku, Azerbaijan. The key outcome of the conference, the Baku Action Plan, sets the global agenda for human-centered digital development. [Read More](#)

Bail as Virtual Acquittal

The constitutional guarantee of personal liberty, enshrined most visibly in India's bail jurisprudence, has been transformed into a political privilege. [Read More](#)

Bangladesh: Crimes Against Humanity

Bangladesh's International Crimes Tribunal has sentenced former PM Sheikh Hasina to death after finding her guilty of alleged crimes against humanity. [Read More](#)

Trump's Russia-Ukraine Strategy

Geopolitical challenge of Russia-Ukraine Conflict. Recent U.S. policy under President Donald Trump has taken several surprising and impactful turns. [Read More](#)

Global Digital Roadmap

The World Telecommunication Development Conference is tasked with setting work priorities for ITU's Telecommunication Development Sector (ITU-D), adopting regional digital development initiatives, and approving formal technical questions. [Read More](#)

Oscar Statuettes Presented to Four Honorees

The Academy of Motion Picture Arts and Sciences held the 16th Governors Awards. Oscar statuettes were presented to four honorees. The ceremony was hosted by Will Arnett, following a welcome delivered by Academy President Lynette Howell Taylor. [Read More](#)

राहुल गांधी को जाना चाहिए

बिहार विधानसभा चुनाव के नतीजों ने कांग्रेस पार्टी को करारी शिकस्त दी है। पार्टी 243 सीटों में से केवल छह सीटों पर ही सिमट कर रह गई। जैसे ही प्रधानमंत्री नरेंद्र मोदी के नेतृत्व वाले राष्ट्रीय जनतांत्रिक गठबंधन (NDA) ने 200 से अधिक सीटों के साथ जीत हासिल की, आलोचक एक बार फिर पार्टी के वास्तविक नेता राहुल गांधी की ओर उंगली उठा रहे हैं। [Read More](#)

Robojit and the Sand Planet Global Media Outreach

Robojit and the Sand Planet, the rising transmedia sci-fi franchise, continues to gain recognition through international interest, emerging partnerships, and cultural localization efforts. The project has launched a comprehensive Press Kit. [Read More](#)

Housing Corruption and Government Carelessness in Delhi

Clean House is a free editorial and advisory public service that empowers residents of Delhi to report corruption and government carelessness affecting their housing and civic life. The service addresses corruption and carelessness of officials. [Read More](#)

Sonia and Rahul Gandhi in National Herald Case

Delhi Police's Economic Offences Wing has filed a fresh First Information Report (FIR) against Sonia Gandhi and Rahul Gandhi in the National Herald case. The new FIR follows a complaint that was routed through the Enforcement Directorate (ED). [Read More](#)

Pakistan's Constitutional Amendments

UN High Commissioner for Human Rights Volker Türk stated that Pakistan's hastily adopted constitutional amendments undermine judicial independence, raising grave concerns regarding military accountability and respect for the rule of law. [Read More](#)

RMN Consumer Rights Network

Its objective is to protect consumers from corporate negligence, misleading advertising, government apathy, and other practices that harm people's rights, health, and financial interests. [Read More](#)

RMN News Audio Reports

To enhance reader engagement, RMN News offers Audio Reports for audio-based analysis of key news stories. These reports are available in English, Hindi, and Punjabi for diverse audience.

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AI Training to Small Businesses

The Pathway training program provides technology, digital marketing, and Artificial Intelligence (AI) training to small- and medium-sized businesses (SMBs) in different industry segments. [Read More](#)

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